

**STRENGTHENING THE RESPONSIBILITY OF CONSUMER PROTECTION OF TRADERS
PROVIDING GOODS AND SERVICES****Pham Tien Dung***PhD., Tran Nhan Tong Institute,
Vietnam National University, Hanoi***Abstract**

The Law on Consumer Rights Protection 2023 stipulates the basic responsibilities of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services such as: responsibility to protect consumer information, responsibility to protect vulnerable consumers, responsibility to resolve complaints, responsibility to recall defective goods, warranty responsibility as well as other related responsibilities when using digital platforms to provide products and goods to consumers. To strengthen the implementation of responsibilities of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services, it is necessary to have the participation of related entities such as management agencies, enterprises, consumers as well as press and media agencies.

Keywords: Consumers, responsibilities of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services, Law on Protection of Consumer Rights.

1. Concept of responsibility of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services according to the provisions of the Law on Protection of Consumer Rights

According to Clause 2, Article 3 of the Law on Consumer Protection 2023, organizations and individuals trading in goods and services are defined as follows:

“Organizations and individuals trading in goods and services are organizations and individuals that continuously carry out one, several or all stages of the process from investment, production to consumption of products, goods or provision of services on the market for the purpose of making a profit, including: Traders as prescribed by the Law on Commerce; Individuals conducting independent and regular commercial activities without having to register for business” (1).

With this definition, regardless of the organization or individual involved, with the ability to make a profit in the process of providing goods and services to consumers, they are subject to the Law on Consumer Protection, which means they must be responsible to consumers..

2. Responsibilities of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services according to the provisions of the Law on Protection of Consumer Rights***Responsibility for ensuring safety, measurement, quantity, volume, quality, and uses of products, goods, and services sold and provided to consumers***

According to Article 14 of the Law on Consumer Protection 2023, when dealing with consumers, organizations and individuals trading in goods and services must ensure the safety, measurement, quantity, volume, quality, and uses of products, goods, and services sold and provided to consumers in accordance with the registered, announced, announced, listed, advertised, introduced, contracted, committed, or as prescribed by law, must warn about products, goods, and services that are likely to cause insecurity, adversely affect the life, health, and property of consumers, and notify about preventive measures as prescribed by law.

Responsibility to protect consumer information

The responsibility to protect consumer information is specifically stipulated in Articles 15 to 20 of the Law on Consumer Protection. According to this provision, organizations and individuals trading in goods and services are responsible for fully informing consumers of the purpose of collecting information, the scope of information use, the period of information storage, developing rules for protecting consumer information and publicly posting them at appropriate locations for consumers to know. During and after entering into contracts with consumers, organizations and individuals trading in goods and services must use the collected consumer information for the stated purpose, must not transfer it to a third party (without the consumer's permission), and must destroy the consumer's information after the information storage period expires.

Responsibility to protect the rights of vulnerable consumers

Vulnerable consumers are consumers who are likely to suffer many adverse impacts on access to information, health, property, and dispute resolution at the time of purchasing or using products, goods, and services, including: Elderly people as defined by the law on the elderly; People with disabilities as defined by the law on the disabled; Children as defined by the law on children; Ethnic minorities; people living in ethnic minority areas and mountainous areas, islands, areas with difficult socio-economic conditions, areas with especially difficult socio-economic conditions as defined by the law; Women who are pregnant or raising children under 36 months old... This can be considered a breakthrough, a new point of the Law on Consumer Rights Protection in 2023, accordingly, when dealing with vulnerable consumers, organizations and individuals trading in goods and services need to have their own policies to give more priority to this group in transactions and in receiving and resolving complaints. In addition, it is also necessary to publicly develop a transaction process with each vulnerable consumer group in the form of posting at the headquarters, business loca-

tions or posting on the electronic information page, application software (if any) and training and coaching for their employees.

Responsibility for resolving consumer disputes

According to the provisions of the Law on Consumer Rights Protection 2023, in case a consumer sends a request for negotiation and related information and documents (if any) to an organization or individual trading in goods and services, the organization or individual is responsible for receiving and negotiating with the consumer. After receiving the request for negotiation from the consumer, the organization or individual trading in goods and services is responsible for negotiating with the consumer within 07 working days. The organization or individual trading in goods and services is responsible for notifying in writing the negotiation results to the state management agency on consumer rights protection and the social organization participating in consumer rights protection within 05 working days from the date of completion of the negotiation (Article 57 of the Law on Consumer Rights Protection). In case of refusing a consumer's request for negotiation, within 07 working days from the date of receipt of the request for negotiation, the business organization or individual must respond in writing and state the reason.

Responsibility for warranty of products, goods, components and accessories

In case the products, goods, components and accessories are subject to warranty, the business organization or individual shall be responsible for: Publicly announcing the warranty policy; Accurately and fully implementing the warranty responsibility for the products, goods, components and accessories provided by them; Providing consumers with a warranty acceptance document or other equivalent form of warranty acceptance, clearly stating the warranty implementation period. The warranty implementation period is not included in the warranty period of the products, goods, components and accessories. In case the business organization or individual replaces components and accessories, the warranty period of those components and accessories shall be recalculated from the time of replacement of components and accessories. In case the business organization or individual exchanges new products and goods, the warranty period of those products and goods shall be recalculated from the time of replacement of new products and goods; Provide consumers with similar products, goods, components, and accessories for temporary use or have a suitable settlement form according to the agreement between the consumer and the business organization or individual during the warranty period; Exchange new similar products, goods, components, and accessories or recall products, goods, components, and accessories and refund consumers in case the warranty period expires without repair or the error cannot be fixed or in case the product, goods, components, and accessories have been warranted 3 times or more during the warranty period but the error still cannot be fixed; Bear the costs of repairing and transporting products, goods, components, and accessories from the consumer's residence or the place of use of the product, goods, components, and accessories to the warranty place and from the warranty

place to the consumer's residence or the place of use of the product, goods, components, and accessories; Responsible for warranty of products, goods, components and accessories for consumers, even in cases where another organization or individual is authorized or hired to perform the warranty.

Responsibility for recalling defective goods

When organizations and individuals trading in goods and services discover that their goods are defective or upon request of a state management agency, organizations and individuals are responsible for recalling defective goods. Defective products and goods are divided into 3 groups: Group A defective products and goods are products and goods that can cause damage to the life and health of consumers; Group B defective products and goods are products and goods that can cause damage to consumers' property; The last group is products and goods with defects that can cause damage to the life, health, and property of consumers. The regulations for products and goods with group A defects apply.

When discovering that their products and goods supplied to the market are defective, business organizations and individuals are responsible for stopping the supply of products and goods to the market, taking measures to recall the goods, announcing information on radio or television, and reporting to the state management agency on consumer rights protection (Article 33 of the Law on Consumer Rights Protection).

Responsibility for recalling defective goods

This responsibility is stipulated in Articles 24 to 28 of the Law on Consumer Protection and Articles 6 to 16 of Decree No. 55/2024/ND-CP detailing a number of articles of the Law on Consumer Protection. Regarding this provision, enterprises using standard contracts and general transaction conditions according to Decision No. 07/2024/QĐ-TTĐ must register standard contracts and general transaction conditions with the state management agency on consumer protection before signing contracts with consumers. For standard contracts, transaction conditions must comply with specific regulations on the language used being Vietnamese, the form of the contract must comply with the provisions of civil law, and the content of the contract must ensure the provisions of the law and ensure a balance of interests between consumers and organizations and individuals trading in goods and services. In case the provisions in the standard contract or general terms of transaction have different interpretations, the interpretation shall be carried out in favor of the consumer.

Corporate Responsibility in Cyberspace

For the first time, the Law on Consumer Protection as well as the Law on Electronic Transactions have mentioned the concept of transactions in cyberspace. According to Clause 1, Article 39 of the Law on Consumer Protection: "Organizations and individuals doing business in cyberspace include: Organizations and individuals doing business in products, goods and services through self-established information systems or through digital platforms; and Organizations establishing and operating intermediary digital platforms" (2). For organizations and individuals operating on digital platforms (including intermediary digital platforms and

large digital platforms), in addition to performing the responsibilities of organizations and individuals doing business in normal goods and services as presented in the above contents, they must perform the following responsibilities:

The organization that establishes and operates the digital intermediary platform has the following responsibilities:

- Designate and publicly announce contact points and authorized representatives to coordinate with competent state agencies in resolving issues related to consumer rights protection;
- Develop and publicly announce regulations on the operation of intermediary digital platforms for consumers, clearly defining the responsibilities of the parties involved in the transaction;
- Provide information about business organizations and individuals operating on intermediary digital platforms when consumers transact with such business organizations and individuals upon request;
- Allow consumers to respond and evaluate business organizations and individuals, products, goods and services sold and provided by business organizations and individuals, and at the same time fully and accurately display the results of feedback and evaluation, except in cases where such feedback and evaluation violates the provisions of law or is contrary to social ethics;
- Fully and transparently display information on products, goods and services sold and provided by business organizations and individuals, including mandatory contents displayed on product labels according to the provisions of law on product labels, except for information of a specific nature according to the product, including: date, month, year of manufacture; expiry date; production batch number; frame number, engine number; performance standards to be achieved in providing products, goods and services;
- Designate and publicly announce a focal point for receiving and resolving consumer feedback, requests and complaints related to products, goods, services, information content on the intermediary digital platform; receive and resolve consumer feedback, requests and complaints against organizations establishing and operating the intermediary digital platform;
- Have measures to allow priority display of assessments, feedback and recommendations of social organizations participating in protecting consumer rights or credit rating organizations according to the provisions of law;
- Directly store information or provide solutions to store information about products, goods, services and related transactions, allowing consumers to access, trace, download, store and print invoices, vouchers and documents related to transactions on the intermediary digital platform that they manage;
- Be transparent about advertising activities on cyberspace according to the provisions of law in case of advertising activities;
- Provide reports on content censorship activities performed at the request of competent state agencies;

- Maintain online reporting accounts and provide updated information and data up to the time of reporting request to serve the inspection and examination activities of competent state management agencies according to the provisions of law;

- Authenticate the identity of organizations and individuals selling products, goods and providing services on their intermediary digital platform;

- Be responsible to consumers according to the provisions of the law on e-commerce in cases where domestic and foreign business organizations and individuals sell and provide products, goods and services to consumers in the territory of Vietnam;

- Perform other responsibilities according to the provisions of this Law and other relevant legal provisions.

In Clause 2, Article 2 of Decree No. 55/2024/ND-CP detailing a number of articles of the Law on Consumer Rights Protection, it is stipulated that: “A large digital platform is a digital platform serving electronic transactions established and operated to serve business activities in cyberspace and meeting one of the following criteria: Having 3,000,000 or more active user accounts annually in Vietnam according to the provisions of the law on electronic transactions. Business organizations and individuals are responsible for determining the number of active user accounts on the digital platform they establish and operate; Or It is a large-scale or very large-scale intermediary digital platform serving electronic transactions according to the provisions of the law on electronic transactions”(3).

Responsibilities of organizations and individuals doing business on large digital platforms

Businesses operating on large digital platforms, in addition to fulfilling their responsibilities as businesses on intermediary digital platforms, need to fulfill the following additional responsibilities:

- Establish an advertising repository using algorithms to target consumers and specific consumer groups;

- Periodically evaluate content moderation activities, the use of algorithmic systems and advertising targeting consumers and specific consumer groups;

- Periodically evaluate the implementation of regulations on handling fake accounts, the use of artificial intelligence, fully or partially automated solutions.

3. Some recommendations to strengthen the implementation of responsibilities of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services.

State management agency

State management agencies play an important and guiding role in promulgating and organizing the implementation of legal documents. To enhance the enforcement of responsibilities of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services, state management agencies (specifically the Ministry of Industry and Trade, the focal point for implementing the Law) need to promote the implementation of activities such as:

- + Promote activities to protect consumer rights in specialized ministries, direct localities nationwide to promote the dissemination of the Law on Consumer Rights Protection into life.

+ Coordinate with industry associations to disseminate legal knowledge to organizations and individuals trading in goods and services to know and implement their responsibilities.

+ Strengthen inspection and supervision, including post-inspection of compliance with the responsibilities of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services according to the provisions of the Law on Consumer Rights Protection 2023.

Business Community

Consumers (customers) are the target of any business organization or individual. In the marketplace, business organizations and individuals use many different methods to understand customer needs, attract customers, gain customer trust, thereby selling goods and services, resulting in increased revenue and profits. In addition to the direct approach as above, good compliance with the provisions of the law on consumer rights protection is one of the effective competitive tools of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services. In order to effectively implement the Law on Consumer Rights Protection, organizations and individuals trading in goods and services themselves need to proactively learn about related responsibilities, thereby building operating procedures for organizations and individuals trading in goods and services in accordance with the law on consumer rights protection. In addition, organizations and individuals trading in goods and services are also the most important subjects in promoting sustainable consumption through further promoting research, development and provision of products and goods in an environmentally friendly direction, using recycled materials, and limiting harmful effects on the environment.

Consumer

In the production and consumption relationship, consumers play a very important role in the existence and development of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services. If consumers do not buy goods and products from organizations and individuals trading in goods and services, it means that organizations and individuals trading in goods and services will not be able to survive in the market. Organizations and individuals trading in goods and services that are trusted and used by consumers are an endless resource, and organizations and individuals trading in goods and services will develop. On their side, consumers also play an important role in supporting organizations and

individuals trading in goods and services to promote compliance with legal regulations on protecting consumer rights through prioritizing the selection of products and services of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services that comply with the provisions of the law on protecting consumer rights.

Media, press

Press and media agencies play a pivotal role in conveying messages from state management agencies about the responsibilities of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services to consumers to social groups, as well as conveying messages from organizations and individuals trading in goods and services to consumers. With their role, press and media agencies need to promptly update the Party's policies and the State's laws to organizations and individuals trading in goods and services, encourage organizations and individuals trading in goods and services to comply with their responsibilities as prescribed by the Law on Consumer Protection, and commend typical examples of organizations and individuals trading in goods and services who do good business and are responsible to consumers.

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